

Promoting Vietnamese Family Culture In The Process Of Globalization

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Abstract

Family is an important environment to form, nurture and educate human personality, preserve and promote good family culture, and fight against social evils. Family is the first place and also the last place to perform emotional and moral education, lifestyle for people in particular, and family culture in general. In the process of international integration, along with the development of social life, the work of caring for and developing family culture has achieved great achievements, contributing to the success of the goal of building a family. Vietnam is prosperous, equal, progressive, civilized, and happy. However, in that context, it also puts family culture in front of changes and many difficulties and challenges. Therefore, building and developing a family culture in the process of international integration is a significant issue in building a healthy cultural environment, which is the mission to found, form personality, and good qualities for the Vietnamese today with the aspiration to build a prosperous and happy nation.

Introduction

The family where people are born, grow up has a unique role and position for each individual, social community, and momentous element of social life. The growth, progress, civilization, prosperity, and happiness in the family are essential measures to evaluate the development of the nation and ethnicity. The family is a "school", a special "cultural institution", the first cradle that contributes to the upbringing and forms good virtues and qualities for each person; It is also starting place, cultivating values, beliefs, dreams, and aspirations; a place to protect, surround, give strength and faith to each person to overcome challenges, constantly grow and make many contributions to society. A family is also a place of hope and a dream of people far from home. We can also think that family is a homeland, where ancestors, grandparents, parents, brothers, relatives, and clans are. For every Vietnamese, the family has a special significance. It is imprinted deeply on the journey of a person's life.

In the process of international integration, the open-door exchange and integration have provided Vietnamese families with conditions for economic development, exchange, and integration with advanced cultures and civilizations of other countries. Positive aspects have arisen many problems affecting Vietnamese family culture, making generations of Vietnamese families face challenges, moreover Vietnamese family cultural values have some changes, and are posing challenges.

Consequently, building and promoting family culture in the process of international integration is an important issue in building a sustainable cultural environment. From identifying the current situation of family culture, the article orients and proposes some solutions to build a family culture in stable development.

The research questions in this study will be:

- What are the results and limitations of implementing Vietnamese family culture in the process of in the process of globalization?
- What are some solutions to promote Vietnamese family culture in the process of in the process of globalization?

Literature Review

It is impossible to ignore the issue of family culture when studying the development of society. Therefore, globally, in Vietnam, the family culture's problem has been studied and investigated by researchers as an object of many scientific disciplines. Family culture has been approached from many different angles with typical works:

World Revolution and Family Patterns by William J. Goode has mentioned the change in a family model in China, Japan, India, Sub-Saharan, and Arab countries during half of the 20th century with changes in the political institutions of each country as well as changes in the region. Accordingly, the author has surveyed and studied the process of industrialization and urbanization affecting all aspects of family life, making changes in

the size, structure, problems of marriage, and relationships in the family... then, new family models are introduced that are suitable for each country and region (Goode, 1963).

Jessie Bernard's *The Future of Marriage* discussed marriage, gender, changes in marital behavior, attitudes, knowledge, and disparities between marriage between men and women. Jessie Bernard also predicts that today's couples are struggling to improve their married life by working together, sharing parenting, and harmoniously combining family bonding responsibilities with personal autonomy... (Bernard, 1982)

Elaine Leeder, *The Family in Global Perspective - A Gendered Journey* has used many different historical viewpoints, theoretics, and comparisons to expand the understanding of family intercultural understanding. The book surveys family cultural diversity in Western countries and contrasts them with family stories in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. After comparing family histories in many parts of the world, Elaine Leeder analyzed the impact of globalization on family culture, family structure, gender behavior, relationships between families generations in the family, ethnicity, religion, ethnicity, and issues of education, violence, social policies related to family life... (Leeder, 2003).

Tran Huu Tong, Truong Thin, *Building a cultural family in the cause of innovation*, analyzed the differences in family, building a family culture in the process of international integration in Vietnam (Tong & Thin, 1997). In the article *The Vietnamese family in the context of a reformed country* by Le Thi, the author pointed out that: Vietnamese families are strongly influenced by contemporary economic and social conditions, but they are stable and stable relatively independent in development. It has its laws of motion, in which, "economic relations do not play the role of the ultimate decisive factor but are blood relations, affection and responsibility" (Thi, 2002). We cannot simply take economic factors and social fluctuations to explain all phenomena occurring in spiritual and emotional life and changing relationships in the family. It is necessary to consider and study changes in structure, function, and family relationships from both sides: internal in each family and the impact of economic and social factors. Moreover, the author analyzed the impact of factors of science, technology, economy, society... that changed the family culture in both positive and negative directions. Therefore, building a family culture today is necessary to harmoniously combine traditional family culture with modern cultural values. Accepting the modern family's spiritual values, which does not contradict the preservation and promotion of the good and inherent moral values of the Vietnamese family.

Hoang BichNga, *To have a cultural family*. The book has analyzed relatively complete factors to have a cultural family such as love and marriage, the development stages of the family; the education of parents towards their children, family relationships such as husband, wife, grandfather, grandmother, child, grandchild, etc. and relations with neighbors, homeland and country. Pass on the book's content, readers can draw the answer "to have a cultural family", each member of the family must perform well their duties and responsibilities towards the family simple, does not engage in unhealthy pleasures, is not far from social evils... The book also clearly shows the important role of the movement to build cultural diversity in the formation and development of Vietnamese families in the new era. It was also synchronizes affirmed that it is necessary to continue to maintain the implementation of the "Movement to build a cultural family" not only in width but also in-depth to achieve the highest results and effectiveness (Nga, 2005).

Vu Ngoc Khanh, *Vietnamese family culture*. The content of his book has analyzed and covered the following aspects: Vietnamese family history from a spiritual basis to create culture; routines and customs; unique features, images imbued with cultural identity; family rituals... The author mentioned the issue of family culture and analyzed its influences from the trends of religion, philosophy, literature - art... through which to learn and preserve cultural Ethnic characteristics are hidden in families (Khanh, 2007).

In addition, there are articles such as Tran ThiTuyet Mai, *Family culture and building a cultural family in the integration period*⁸, which mentioned the role of family and family culture; point out the advantages and disadvantages of family and family culture in the face of challenges of the integration process; draw out the contents of cultural family values and build family cultural values in the new period (Mai, 2008).

Thus, it can be seen that, by collecting overview documents, the research has provided me with valuable materials to clarify the goals and duties of the article to promote Vietnamese family culture in the process of integration international.

Research Method

Family culture is a system of cultural values integrated from the traditional and modern cultural values of a nation, expressing the awareness, attitude, and behavior of members in the implementation of family functions and behavior in personal - family - social relationships to build a prosperous, equal, progressive, and happy family.

If Western society dignifies individual values, Eastern cultural traditions, including Vietnam, tend to promote community values, family tradition, and clans - an interacted space and the first connection of humans before entering society. Along with the historical ups and downs, generations of families have made massive contributions to the success of the revolution, resistance war, and the cause of national construction and defense in the current period. The cohesion of the model "House - Village - Homeland" has become a "cultural

constant", which is a fine tradition, showing the strong attachment of each family to the countryside. Keep the homeland to keep the village, keep the home; and protecting villages is also protecting the country and homeland.

Pass through many ups and downs times, the good traditions of the family have crystallized into a sustainable value system, which is patriotism, the tradition of solidarity, and sticking together; is love, care, protection, fond of learning, honor, etc. Today, which are still conserved, promoted, spread, and simultaneously constantly creating. And adding values, new cultural standards, they are prosperous, happy, progressive, and civilized families. Those grateful values are cultivated over many generations, stages, and periods, creating a strong bond between members and generations, which makes the traditional family culture flow unbroken a segment that always has a regular, continuous continuity.

Aware of the importance of family culture for sustainable socio-economic development, Vietnam has affirmed: "Building a prosperous, progressive and happy family is a healthy cell strength of society, is an important environment, directly educating lifestyles, shaping personality... Vietnamese people and culture" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2011, p.77). At the same time, "Focus on researching, identifying and implementing the building of a national value system, a cultural value system and human standards associated with preserving and developing the Vietnamese family value system in the new period. Implement Vietnamese family culture standards of prosperity, happiness, progress, and civilization. To dignify the role of the family in nurturing and educating the young generation" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021, p.143- 144).

On that basis, the Vietnamese government has issued policies, strategies, and projects to develop family culture such as Directive No. 49-CT/TW dated February 21, 2005, of the Central Committee on the development of family culture, building a family in the period of national industrialization and modernization; Resolution No. 21-NQ/TW dated October 25, 2017, of the Party Central Committee on population work in the new situation; Decision No. 629/QĐ-TTg dated May 29, 2012, of the Prime Minister approving the Strategy for Vietnam's Family Development to 2020, with a Vision to 2030; Laws directly related to family work such as Law on Marriage and Family (2000), Law on Gender Equality (2006), Law on Prevention and Control of Domestic Violence (2007), Law on Protection, Care and Children's education (2004), Youth Law (2005, revised in 2020), which emphasizes: "Family is the cell of society, an important environment for character formation, nurturing and education, preserving and promoting good traditional culture, fighting social evils, creating human resources to serve the cause of national construction and defense", "Building a prosperous and progressive Vietnamese family". Happiness is everyone's nest, a healthy cell of society" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2005).

The article is based on dialectical materialism, viewpoints, and policies of Vietnam on promoting Vietnamese family culture in the process of international integration. At the same time, the article also uses synthesis of specific research methods such as history, logic, comparison, analysis, synthesis, induction and deduction, data synthesis... to serve the research and present articles.

Results and Discussion

Results and limitations of implementing Vietnamese family culture in process of in the process of globalization

Vietnam's economy in the integration process has spectacular development steps, achieved many achievements of historical significance. The economic growth rate has been rather high for many years, the scale of the economy has been much larger than before. Gross domestic product (GDP) grew at an average annual rate of 6.6% in the period (1986 - 2017) and reached 6% per year in the period (2016-2020). Although heavily effects by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, with this growth rate, Vietnam belongs to the high-growth countries group in the region and the world. Compared with some countries with fast economic growth in the world over the past 35 years, the average GDP growth rate of Vietnam is only behind China at 9.4%, ahead of South Korea and Malaysia at 5.9%, on Thailand is 5.2%, in the US it is 2.6%, Japan is 1.7% and Germany is 1.8%. Vietnam's economic scale has increased from 90th place in the world in 1990 to 171.2 billion USD, ranked 57th in the world in 2013. Vietnam from a country in the group of poorest countries in the world has become a country low-middle income countries in 2008.

High economic growth has contributed to improving the material and spiritual life of many households. If 2007 back before, Vietnam was a low-income country with a per capita income of less than \$1,000/person/year, then from 2008, Vietnam became a low-middle-income country, with a low-middle-income country per capita is 1,154 USD/person/year and increase to 2,779 USD/person/year in 2020 (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021, p.43). The increase in family income has facilitated access to all kinds of services in education, culture, entertainment, and tourism for each family member, which has also expanded, contributing to raising the standard of living awareness, understanding capacity, life mastery skills, and good handling of complex situations that arise. Also according to the General Statistics Office's assessment of the education quality nationwide: "The education level has improved, the proportion of the population aged 15 and over who can read and write has increased sharply; Most children of primary school age are attending school, and the proportion of

out-of-school children has fallen sharply over the past decade. Nationally, about 91.7% of the population of high school age is currently attending school. The overall attendance rate of primary school is 101.0%, secondary school is 92.8%, high school is 72.3%. In the whole country, 95.8% of people aged 15 years and over can read and write, an increase of 1.8 percentage points compared to 2009” (General Statistics Office, 2020).

Up to now, most households are living in permanent or semi-permanent houses (93.1%); The system of cultural, educational, and medical institutions has been invested and built, (99.7%) of communes have primary schools and kindergartens; 99.5% of communes have health stations; 58.6% of communes have cultural houses, thereby contributing to increasing the average life expectancy of people, from 72.9 age in 2010 to 73.7 age in 2020. These are favorable conditions for each family member to develop comprehensively, have time to take care and attend to a happy and prosperous family.

Moreover, in the current global exchange and integration context, with the efficient support of information technology, the internet, the experiences, knowledge, and historical lessons of humanity are widely published; the beauties in the behavioral culture of family models belonging to the regional and international communities and ethnic groups were introduced and spread; along with that are new cultural values that are produced and created... That is a rich and massive amount of knowledge that each member of a Vietnamese family can easily access to manipulate and reflect into Vietnamese family culture, thereby seeing similarities and differences, unique and typical values of family traditions that need to be preserved, preserved, and promoted; Old and outdated values need to be identified to eliminate and especially to be selective and adopt new, progressive and civilized values that families around the world are doing. According to statistics, there are currently about 68 million Vietnamese using the internet, tens of million people have Facebook accounts with a large amount of interaction time in cyberspace, and young people's foreign language ability has been improved (Government, 2020). These are favorable conditions in expanding exchanges, learning the quintessence of human culture, studying, applying, and absorbing values belonging to the family cultural life of countries in the region and the world.

On the other hand, with the attention and direction of the Vietnamese government, with many policies, resolutions, strategies, projects, and laws directly related to the Family culture has been diffused, widely propagated to families in all regions of the country, creating a great change in the awareness of the whole political system, government at all levels and public about the role and position of the construction and development of Vietnamese family culture in the new era with movements such as All people unite to build cultural life: All people unite to build new rural and urban areas civilized town; grandparents, exemplary parents, and good children; raise healthy children, teach good children; family, lineage studious; family culture; cultural villages... have created exciting competitions, attracting a large number of members and families to participate, contributing to building an increasingly prosperous, equal, and progressive family ministry, civilization; preserve, uphold and promote the beautiful culture of family traditions and clans.

Judging one of the outstanding achievements in family work over the past time, the 13th Party Congress emphasized: "In the context of isolation and social distancing due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, it has emerged cultural values, social ethics, good family traditions; many examples of good people, good deeds are replicated and promoted" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2011, vol 2, p.48).

However, there are still limitations and challenges:

- While the people's material and spiritual life is getting higher and higher, family morality has gradually degraded expression, family cultural values are being turned upside down, traditional family life is in danger of dying down Meanwhile, the new cultural values of modern families are not strong enough to be affirmed in modern social life, so generations of family members are vulnerable and separated: some elderly people live alone lack of attentive care of children and relatives; there is a situation of homeless children making a living on their own, so they easily fall into social evils, domestic violence, divorce is increasing, creating strong conflicts in the morality of husband and wife making children after their parents' divorce did not receive a healthy moral education, children are more prone to causing disruptive behavior, depression, even crime, the tendency of juvenile commit crimes is coming high increases...

- With the opposite side of the industrial revolution 4.0 has been creating gaps between members and generations. The level of interaction, exchange, and sharing traditionally is increasingly limited because young people spend too much time on virtual interactions in cyberspace, pursuing personal passions and habits without neglecting them to forget connection with family members and in society. In the space of many urban families today, each person have a distinct and closed world that lead to a situation parents and children do not understand each other, parents lack attention, causing young people to fall into difficult situations traps, temptations, deviant actions that adults cannot anticipate to prevent.

- Besides the families who still maintain filial piety, overcome difficulties, live with ambition, there has appeared a pragmatic, liberal lifestyle, disregarding or ignoring filial piety, family etiquette, and irresponsibility responsibility to family and community, living coldly and alienating those who are facing a life of poverty. There is a situation of children wandering to earn a living and plunge into social evils, some elderly people live

alone without the care of their children and relatives. Social evils, domestic violence, drug prostitution are invading and disrupting family happiness.

- Previously, in the traditional family model, many generations lived under one roof, everyone behaved with rituals and rules according to the regulations on hierarchy, clear hierarchy, and roles; Individual behavior is adjusted by ethical standards, public opinion, and regulations in village conventions and rules. However, at present, along with the process of integration and urbanization, the fast pace of life of modern society and the influence of exchanges and contact with Western culture, the traditional family model of three, The four great streets are gradually narrowing, giving way to the presence of nuclear families (husband and wife - children), along with the architectural model of families' houses also changing. Mixed with positive signals, modern families also have to face many new and complicated problems such as single-parent family models, separation, same-sex families appearing more and more, a great influence on the maintenance of the race, bloodline and the education and cultural transmission to the younger generation.

- Vietnam is in the golden population period and is beginning to approach the aging population. Without good coping scenarios, the number of elderly people falling into a state of loneliness and helplessness will occur. A part of the elderly in some urban areas and cities is currently facing the situation of lack of care and upbringing of children in the family, lack of necessary cultural institutions outside the family to serve the needs of living, playing, entertaining, improving health, and spiritual life.

Some solutions to promote Vietnamese family culture in process of in the process of globalization

- It is necessary to unify the awareness about "Building a prosperous, progressive and happy Vietnamese family, truly a home for each person, a healthy cell of society, an important resource for economic development socio-economic. "Family happiness" must be protected by the legal system and related documents under the law. Continue to implement the contents of the Vietnam Family Strategy for the period 2010-2020, with a vision to 2030. Implement and well implement the provisions in the system of mechanisms, policies, and laws on public affairs. The family partnership has been promulgated by the State, paying special attention to ensuring the rights, responsibilities, and obligations of each member towards the family, community, and society. At the same time, research, supplement and adjust the terms that have become inadequate. Forecasting new trends and scenarios that families will face, thereby building appropriate and timely mechanisms and policies. There are forms of handling, education, and deterrence against acts that violate social ethical standards and the law on family work.

It is necessary to soon identify and push back the ideas and concepts that have become inadequate and outdated, inhibiting the development of individuals and families, such as the idea of respecting men and disrespecting women, the imposition of the previous generation, patriarchy, local factionalism, the habit of relying on, covering... which is a necessary and meaningful job. At the same time, constantly absorbing and adding new and progressive values through the process of exchanging and learning with countries in the region and the world based on traditional cultural values, such as the spirit of democracy, freedom in creativity, respect for human rights, a civilized way of life according to the law, attaching personal responsibility to the community and society; well enforce discipline and discipline; have proactive spirit, have the knowledge, bravery, and experience to deal with new and complicated situations that arise.

- Continue to maintain and develop the movement of building a cultural family, upholding the building of family culture and criteria for a happy family. Maintain the reward and honor system on time, periodically organize the commendation and replication of outstanding typical examples on a large scale as the core for all places to follow. The movement to build a cultural family is the quintessence of the new culture; an effective educational environment in building new people; a solid fortress against all kinds of social evils. Family and cultural values of the new era need to be honored, propagated, and promoted widely. There must be a plan to prevent the negative social encroachment into the family that reduces the value of Vietnamese family culture. Provide specific guidance, effectively prevent and fight powerful against the negatives, customs, and evils that are happening to Vietnamese families.

- Promoting the spirit of exemplary family of previous generations; building, forming and spreading the role model of ideal people with a good personality, quality, morals, intellectual talents, actions, and beautiful lifestyles in social life to spread messages Humanities. Promoting the role and mission of educational institutions in the transmission of knowledge and experiences with the family educational environment together, which contribute to form new people, who continue to build a better life.

Conclusion

Family is the place people were born, grow up, and there, they have had received the first lessons about family culture in particular and national culture in general. Through the ups and downs of history, generations of Vietnamese families have created and formed good cultural values, becoming a strength and spiritual fulcrum for each individual, then they constantly grow, develop, and contribute to society. Nowadays, those precious values need to be spread and promoted strongly to educate and shape the personality, qualities, and good virtues of each person - It means the most significant resource to ensure the process is fast-growing and sustainable in

our country. However, in the process of international integration, some challenges require synchronous solutions to promote family culture, ensuring that there are prosperous, happy, and progressive families for each family's efforts, it is very necessary to have the maximum investment support and protection of the State and the law. In conclusion, Vietnamese families are enough conditions for sustainable development, Vietnamese family culture will be a core part of the national culture and serve as the foundation for a stable society.

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